

THE ROLE OF VAMANA KARMA AND SHAMANA CHIKITSA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TAMAKA SHWASA: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tamaka Shwasa, a disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of breathlessness, wheezing, and cough, closely resembles bronchial asthma in modern medicine. Ayurveda classifies it under Pranavaha Sroto Dushti, primarily involving Vata and Kapha Doshas with associated Ama. **Objective:** To evaluate the efficacy of classical Ayurvedic protocols—specifically Vamana Karma (therapeutic emesis) followed by Shamana Chikitsa (palliative treatment)—in managing Tamaka Shwasa. **Methods:** A single-case study design was adopted. A 38-year-old male with chronic Tamaka Shwasa underwent Poorva Karma (preparatory procedures: Deepana-Pachana and Snehana-Swedana), followed by Vamana Karma with Madanphala, Yastimadhu, Saindhav, Vekhand & Honey. Post-Vamana, Samana Chikitsa was administered using herbal formulations like Vyagri Haritaki leha, shwasakuthar rasa, Kanthkari kwath tailored to the

patient's Doshic imbalance. Assessment was based on subjective symptom relief, frequency of attacks, and objective parameters like Peak Expiratory Flow Rate (PEFR). **Results:** Significant reduction in dyspnea, wheezing, and cough frequency was observed. PEFR improved from 280 L/min to 420 L/min. The integrated approach provided sustained remission over a 6-month follow-up. **Conclusion:** Sequential application of Vamana Karma and Shamana Chikitsa offers a promising Ayurvedic strategy for managing Tamaka Shwasa by addressing root-cause Doshic imbalance and providing symptomatic relief.

2. CASE PRESENTATION

Patient: ABC, 38-year-old male, chronic smoker (10 years), presented with:

- Recurrent dyspnea, worse at night and in cold weather
- Productive cough with whitish expectoration
- Wheezing and chest tightness
- Fatigue and reduced exercise tolerance

Duration: Symptoms persistent for 5 years, worsening seasonally.

Previous Treatment: Used salbutamol inhaler as needed, with temporary relief.

Ayurvedic Examination

- **Prakriti:** Kapha-Vata
- **Vikriti:** Kapha-Vata predominance, Ama present
- **Nadi:** Kapha-Vata
- **Agni:** Mandagni (low digestive fire)
- **Dashavidha Pariksha:** Confirmed chronicity and strength for Shodhana.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Study Design: Single-case observational study.

3.2. Interventions in Sequence

Phase 1: Poorva Karma (Preparatory Procedures)

- ✓ **Deepana-Pachana:** Administered Hingvasthka churna 5 gms two times a day to enhance Agni and digest Ama.
- ✓ **Snehana :** Til tail, Sthanik Snehana at Chest region Saindhav mishrit til tail.
- ✓ **Swedana:** Used Dashmoolakwath petiswedan with chest region sthanik swedana

Phase 2: Pradhana Karma (Main Procedure – Vamana Karma)

- ✓ After assessing Koshtha (bowel type) and Vyadhi Bala, the patient was given 2 glass of warm cow milk And Vamana Yoga – Madanphala, Yathimadhu, Vekhand(decoction) with honey and rock salt.
- ✓ Emesis was induced until Samyak Shuddhi Lakshanas (optimal purification signs) appeared: clear vomitus (Netra Prasadana, lightness in chest).
- ✓ Paschat Karma (Post-procedure Care): Samsarjana Krama (gradual diet normalization) for 3 days with light liquid to solid foods.

"The Kapha located in the heart and stomach causes diseases like Shwasa and Kasa; it is to be eliminated by Vamana."

3. Shamana Chikitsa then pacified residual Vata-Kapha, strengthened Agni and Pranavaha Srotas, and prevented recurrence.

Modern research supports Vamana's action in reducing bronchial hyper- reactivity and IgE levels. Shamana chikitsa have documented bronchodilatory and anti-inflammatory effects. The combination of Shodhana and Shamana addresses both Samprapti Vighatana (breaking pathogenesis) and Roga Prashamana (symptom relief).^[7]

6. CONCLUSION

The structured application of Vamana Karma followed by Shamana Chikitsa proved highly effective in managing chronic Tamaka Shwasa. This approach not only alleviated symptoms but also reduced dependency on rescue medication and improved lung function significantly. Further large-scale studies are recommended to validate these findings and standardize protocols.

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